

Public Perception towards Goods and Service Tax (GST) in Tenkasi Taluk

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Abstract

India has witnessed substantial reforms in indirect taxes over the past two decades with the replacement of several tax systems. Introduction of the Value Added Tax (VAT) at the Central and the State level has been considered to be a major step in the globe of indirect tax reforms in India. If the VAT is a major improvement over the pre-existing Central excise duty at the national level and the sales tax system at the State level, then the Goods and Services Tax (GST) will indeed be an additional important perfection-the next logical step-towards a widespread indirect tax reforms in the county. This paper aims to impact and implementation of GST, analyse of perception of GST.

Keywords: Indirect Tax, Features of GST, Advantages, Perceptions of GST.

Introduction

Developing country strive to achieve economic growth and development. Tax reforms are necessary for meeting budgetary deficit. The Indian tax structure allows two type of taxes –direct & indirect tax. Direct taxes is levied directly on individuals and corporate entities. Indirect taxes are those taxes which have their primary burden or impact on a single person. But that person succeeds in shifting his burden to others. Indirect taxes are shifted and the incidence of these taxes falls on persons other than the original payers. Indirect taxes of the Union Government comprise Customs duty, Excise duty, CST and Service Tax.

Indirect taxes are convenient for both the tax-payer and the government. As taxes are paid only when goods are purchased, so, tax-payer does not feel the burden of the tax. This tax is convenient to the government as it collects the amount directly from producers or importers.

Statement of the Problem

Taxes Central Excise, Service Tax, VAT etc., is levied by the Central and State Governments are multistage value added taxes. Before introduction of VAT in Sales Tax and CENVAT in Central Excise and Service Tax, the tax system is very complex and has cascading effect. The product or services are taxed on various stages or destinations. The tax levied at one destination is also be taxed on

another destination. In recent past there is much significant progress in the taxation scenario, which not only improved the tax structure by using new and improved technologies. Such multiplicity of taxes distorts the tax structure and brings in complexities. In order to avoid the cascading effect of duties/taxes the government has introduced the scheme of CENVAT in Central Excise and VAT in states. GST is one indirect tax for the whole nation, which will make India one unified common market. It is a multi-stage, destination-based tax that will be levied on every value addition. The tax regime which was initiated by the UPA government has been put into force by the Narendra Modi government tonight. Thus the researcher has made an attempt to know about “a study on public perception towards Goods and Service Tax (GST) in Tenkasi Taluka”

Objectives of the Study

- To have an overview about the Indirect Tax
- To highlight the features of GST
- To evaluate the advantages and challenges of GST
- To analyse the public perception towards GST in Tenkasi Taluka

Limitation

The period of study is six months. So wide geographical area was not covered and is focused only in Tenkasi.

As the study has done during 2017-2018, the data collected are not accurate due to the limited period.

It is difficult to get information on the GST modified method of tax.

There is a need to inform the public about the details of the GST.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study conducted by the researcher is both descriptive and analytical in nature. The data used are both primary and secondary data. The data were collected from 120 respondents in Tenkasi area through Convenience Random sampling techniques.

Primary Data

Primary data are those which are collected for the first time and thus happens to be original in character. Primary data is collected through interview schedule method.

Secondary Data

Secondary data on the other are those which have already been collected by someone else and which have already been passed through statistical process. Secondary data are compiled from magazine, journal, newspaper, website and book.

Tools of Analysis

The data are analyzed with the help of the tools such as percentage analysis, Weighted average ranking, Mean score methods, diagram and pie charts.

Analysis and Interpretation**Opinion Towards Merits of Indirect Tax**

S. No	Merits	I	II	III	IV	V	Mean score	Rank
1	Convenient	60*5 300	14*4 56	19*3 57	17*2 34	10*1 10	3.80	1
2	Wide coverage	18*5 90	13*4 52	22*3 66	29*2 58	38*1 38	2.53	4
3	Force saving	12*5 60	18*4 72	13*3 39	27*2 54	50*1 50	2.29	5
4	Popularity	11*5 55	42*4 168	39*3 117	21*2 42	7*1 7	3.24	2
5	Shifting of tax burden	32*5 160	20*4 80	22*3 66	31*2 62	15*1 15	3.19	3

Source: primary data

The merits of indirect tax was analysed with the help of Mean Score Ranking method, the table reflects that convenient was given 1st rank by the respondents towards the merits of indirect tax, the popularity was given 2nd rank, shifting of tax burden was given 3rd rank, wide coverage was given 4th rank, force saving was given 5th rank by the respondents towards the merits of indirect tax.

Awareness of Respondents towards GST

S. No	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	106	88.33
2	No	14	11.67
Total		120	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table reflects that out of 120 respondents, 88.33 per cent of the respondents are aware about GST and the remaining 11.67 per cent of the respondents are not aware about GST.

Implementation of GST in Tenkasi Taluka

S. No	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	100	83.33
2	No	20	16.67
Total		120	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table reflects that out of 120 respondents, 83.33 per cent of the respondents agreed with the implementation of GST in Tenkasi Taluka, 16.67 per cent of the respondents disagreed with the implementation of GST in Tenkasi Taluka

Perception of GST

S. No	Perception	I	II	III	IV	V	Mean score	Rank
1	GST is very good tax reform for India	34*5 170	20*4 40	29*3 87	29*2 58	8*1 8	3.02	6
2	GST has increased the legal compliances	38*5 190	14*4 56	25*3 75	27*2 54	16*1 16	3.25	4

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3	GST has increased the tax burden on businessman	31*1 31	13*2 26	43*3 129	24*4 96	9*5 45	2.72	8
4	GST has increased the tax burden on common man	6*1 6	19*2 38	22*3 66	33*4 132	40*5 200	3.68	1
5	India is not ready for implementing GST	4*1 4	39*2 78	19*3 57	43*4 172	15*5 75	3.21	5
6	Government has imposed GST on people without any preparation	32*1 32	20*2 40	22*3 66	31*4 134	15*5 75	2.89	7
7	GST is very difficult to understand	35*1 35	13*2 26	49*3 147	9*4 36	14*5 70	2.61	10
8	GST will increase the inflation (prices) in the country	12*1 12	33*2 66	9*3 27	39*4 156	27*5 135	3.30	2
9	GST is beneficial in long-term	8*5 40	11*4 44	21*3 63	47*2 94	33*1 33	2.28	11
10	GST will increase the tax collection of the government	22*5 110	44*4 176	15*3 45	23*2 46	16*1 16	3.27	3
11	GST affects small business	20*1 20	31*2 62	50*3 150	9*4 36	10*5 50	2.65	9

Source: primary data

The perception of GST was analysed with the help of Mean Score Ranking method, the table reflects that GST has increased the tax burden on common man was given 1st rank by the respondents towards the perception of GST, GST will increase the inflation (price) in the country was given 2nd rank, GST will increase the tax collection of the government was given 3rd rank, GST has increased the legal compliances was given 4th rank, India is not ready for implementing GST was given 5th rank, GST is very good tax reform for India was given 6th rank, Government has imposed GST on people without any preparation was given 7th rank, GST has increased the tax burden on business was given 8th rank, GST affects small business was given 9th rank, GST is very difficult to understand was given 10th rank, and GST is beneficial in long-term was given 11th rank by the respondents towards the perception of GST.

Findings

The following are the findings of the study:

- 40 per cent of the respondents earn below Rs 15000 as their income.
- Convenient was given 1st rank by the respondents towards the merits of indirect tax.
- Multiplicity of duties was given 1st rank by the respondents towards the issues with current indirect tax.
- 83.33 per cent of the respondents agreed with the implementation of GST in Tenkasi Taluka.
- 61.67 per cent of the respondents agreed with the implementation of GST system.
- 55 per cent of the respondents have unknown about the details of GST registration.
- 73.33 per cent of the respondents opined that GST is the burden of consumer.
- 58.33 per cent of the respondents are agreed that the implementation of GST will cause higher price of goods & service.
- 63.33 per cent of the respondents opined positively towards the exploitation of consumers by the retailers by the name of GST.
- Uniform tax rate was given 1st rank by the respondents towards the benefits of GST.

- 35 per cent of the respondents opinion towards the impact of GST in Indian economy is strengthening the economy.
- 28.33 per cent of the respondents opined that GST shall modified make it more suitable for poor people also.

Suggestions

The following are the suggestions of the study

- The public suggested that there should be a smooth, transparent and simple transition provisions which is easily understandable.
- It is suggested that the awareness towards GST should be provided to the illiterate and the women community.
- It is also suggested that the government should come forward to take short films with respect to the new GST and screen the same in familiarized televisions.
- The educated should provide awareness to the general public so as to promote economic development and overall growth of the nation.
- Even the educated and the business people are not aware of the various important issues in the new GST, so the Government should take necessary steps to make familiarize the concepts of the new GST in India..
- GST is the future tax. GST law should therefore have forward looking and open for futuristic businesses such as e-commerce, technology based, IT etc and recognize internet, digital economy, start ups etc.,
- An expert panel should be formed to draft the suitable enabling provision for the concurrent taxation powers and recommend consequential modifications to the Constitutions and it should be published for the mass public.
- GST can also be used as an effective tool for fiscal policy management if implemented successfully due to nation-wide same tax rate.

Conclusion

A great revolution is yet to take place in the near future in the indirect tax system i.e. GST, so the general public is almost unaware of the concepts. But, India being a democratic country should make clear to its citizens about the emerging amendments. Therefore, it is the need of each and every citizen to have awareness about the new GST To rationalize indirect tax structure the proposed GST regime is a half-hearted attempt. In all over the world more than 150 countries have implemented GST. There is a need to study the GST regime set up by various countries by the government of India and also their various effect before implementing it. Also the government should provide some relaxation to farmers and small businessman in Goods and service tax, so that there will be lesser impact on their income in future.

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